

War, what's it good for? Absolutely nothing!

Steven Thomson

Senior Agricultural Economist and Policy Advisor
Scotland's Rural College

Article first published in Farm North East (Ed:
Gillanders, E.) Issue No: 110, April 2022

As I sit and watch in astonishment that war has returned to Europe, it is hard to fathom the hardship that Ukrainian families have had to endure these last months, being torn away from their normal lives. Whilst we admire the courage of those defending their country, and have deepest sympathy to those having to flee their homes, separated from families, I still wonder if the West is doing enough. It has been heartening to hear of so many Scottish farming families opening their doors to Ukrainian refugees – chapeau!

I don't need to explain the impacts that this Russian war is having on the farming community – surges in red diesel and fertiliser costs being the most immediate and obvious. The energy crisis is likely to last for a prolonged period as the economic sanctions against Russia are likely to be long-lived, or at least continue until there is regime change. Whilst the UK does not rely on Russian gas and oil (less than 4% and 8% of our supply respectively) we operate in a global market place, where the impacts of the war are abundantly apparent.

Even before Russia had invaded Ukraine, they had imposed fertiliser export quotas to protect their domestic market. Global fertiliser prices have been significantly affected firstly by the energy crisis, and secondly from heavy reliance on Russian and Belarusian exports. Russia accounted for 17% of global nitrogen in 2019 (the top global exporter) and Belarus and Russia were the second and third largest exporters of potash behind Canada. The Agriculture Industries Confederation reported that Scotland used over 150k tonnes of N, 46k tonnes of P and 69k tonnes of K in 2018-19. The UK is exposed to the international market for fertilisers (we import about 60% of supply) and importers had already been holding back on purchases before Christmas amongst fears that high prices (driven by energy costs) could affect farmer demand and leave them with big losses. Jo Gilbertson (head of fertilizers at AIC) highlighted: *"as an importer you have to balance the risk of buying the fertilizer at global prices against the risk of being able to sell it when farmers are reluctant to buy"*. The outlook for fertilisers looks glum as it is likely there will be a prolonged period of high prices. Using N as an example a jump in cost of £400/tonne equates to £60m additional outgoings from Scottish farmers in fertiliser costs at 2019 usage levels.

Russia and Ukraine are also global powerhouses in the international grains markets. Russia was the largest global wheat exporter and Ukraine was fifth meaning the war (and sanctions) are going to significantly impact on supplies from the region this year. Ukraine banned exports of wheat early into the war to ensure domestic supply and they also restricted sunflower oil exports (leading to cooking oil price spikes in some countries). In addition to these Russian-made disruptions, it is reported that the winter wheat crop in China (the world's largest grain producer) is expected to be very poor as result of heavy rains impacting plantings. Further parts of the US grain-belt are experiencing prolonged droughts that means US wheat reserves are already at a 14-year low.

Amongst the realisation of the impacts that the war in Ukraine may have for food price inflation a number of Governments are looking for solutions to protect their domestic markets. For example, Indonesia has increased its required volume for domestic supply of palm oil (the largest producer of the most consumed vegetable oil in the world). Argentina has banned exports of soyabean oils and maize to protect their domestic markets. There have been discussions in the USA about releasing land that is currently protected under the federal land conservation programme back into cultivation. Whilst Ireland has ruled out compulsory crop growing in response to the ongoing input-costs and food-security crisis, officials have said that arable farmers may yet be encouraged to grow more crops. The Irish and the EU are still considering options for set-aside and ecological focus areas and the EU is establishing a state aid Temporary Crisis Framework to support the EU economy in the wake of Russia's invasion of Ukraine. This would allow *"support for undertakings directly or indirectly affected by the crisis, including farmers and fishers, in the form of liquidity support and aid for increased gas and electricity costs."*

Further, the largest party in the European Parliament, the European People's Party, wants to put a hold on the implementation of the European Union's Farm to Fork Strategy, calling on the EU Commission to produce a *"European strategic food safety plan with reliable forecasts and concrete measures to address this situation on a sector-by-sector basis"* and provide certainty *"that this war will not lead to empty plates in Europe."*

Contrasted to these actions the Defra Minister's recent statements on manure trading and output price increases more than offsetting Basic Payment reductions shows how out of touch he, and his department, are from the reality of farm business. The lack of common sense to even acknowledge that input availability and cost inflation negate these output price increases is galling and worrisome. It will be interesting to see how Rishi Sunak deals with fuel duty in his Spring Budget.

In Scotland, in response to a Parliamentary question, Mairi Gougeon rejected, the call from NFUS to scrap Ecological Focus Area rules this year – sticking to the Scottish Government's long-term position that farming, climate and biodiversity must go hand-in-hand for the long-term resilience of the sector. She did however remind everyone that there were different EFA options to choose from that can add some flexibility. The Scottish Government has, however, established a Food Security and Supply Taskforce jointly with industry to *"monitor, identify and respond to these issues"*. The task force will be co-chaired by Mairi Gougeon and James Withers.

As all of this mulls in my head I come back to that song from my youth – War (what's it good for, absolutely nothing). The lyrics appear as pertinent today as they did back then post-Vietnam. The last couple of months surely must make the UK Government sit up and take stock of their cheap food strategy that is heavily reliant on global imports. Laissez-faire trade policies regarding food security have never worked well over prolonged periods – even when the UK had the Commonwealth to call-on. Global geo-political instability is a disruptive factor that has led to an energy crisis and an emerging food crisis. These are interlinked, and if you throw in climate change to the mix then we really need a full and proper assessment of food risks that the UK/Scotland may face in the next 10-20 years. That may mean reconsidering what we produce as a country (especially biofuels), if we can we do things differently, with less reliance on imported machinery, inputs, energy, etc.

On a more positive, unrelated, end note I was pleased to hear that some framework for future Scottish agricultural policy is now emerging from officials at a recent ARIOB

meeting where Andrew Moxey and myself were presenting thoughts on the future of agricultural policy in Scotland – where attainment of “conditions” regarding greenhouse gas emissions (think of technical efficiency) and biodiversity will be rewarded.